

Concentration dependence of reaction rates and mechanism^{†≠}

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1. Introduction

The evaluation of mechanism of a chemical reaction has been a fascinating problem ever since the first reaction was discovered. After the discovery of a host of reactions, the chemists realised that a probable picture of the mechanism can not be known unless the intimate knowledge of the structure of matter and chemical bonding are fully understood. An understanding of these two therefore became essential and these two have helped a long way in revealing the mysteries of mechanism of reactions. With the advent of various sophisticated techniques for the determination of structure, such as NMR, ESR and other spectroscopies, electron microscope, magnetic balance etc., it has been possible to know the near-real picture of the mechanism of chemical reactions. Although it may be gratifying to make a statement like this, a fact not to be forgotten is that one can possibly see the structure of matter and obtain photographs with the help of present-day techniques, it is not possible to see the course of chemical reaction and one has to rely on indirect evidences in support of a mechanism. The question is, how much should we depend on indirect evidences? No clearcut answer to this question can be given. The only course left for us is to obtain more evidences from as diversified sources as possible in support of a particular mechanism, thus strengthening the already existing ideas. There is also a likelihood that in doing so, a chemist may find to his utter surprise evidences against the current concepts, but then he has an opportunity to propose a modified or alternative mechanism for the reaction under question.

Before discussing the mechanism of reactions at length, the concerning question is : what constitutes the mechanism? Does it mean what bonds are being broken and formed? Does it mean to know and isolate the intermediates? Does it involve one or more steps before yielding the final products? What are the species participating in the various steps? What is the nature of the species? These are some of the aspects

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

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of the mechanism with which a chemist may be concerned, but the latest trend has been to describe the mechanism in terms of the structure of the transition state. Transition state is a term which has significance in the derivation of the rate expression and hence its description mainly rests on the results of kinetics study.

The postulation of suitable mechanism of a reaction has always been a tedious problem for a chemist. Even though one may be aware of the working tools or methods for elucidating the mechanism, sometimes one does not quite understand how to write down the various steps of the mechanism consistent with the experimental results. The problem of knowing the mechanism is therefore, two-fold for a chemist. Firstly, he is faced with the question : what are the suitable tools which he should exploit and which are likely to yield desired results? The second problem which is more challenging, is the interpretation of the rate data on the basis of known theories in such a way that one can propose a probable mechanism. The various ways or methods by which the mechanism of a reaction may be evaluated, are the following : (i) determination of stoichiometry, (ii) analysis of the products, (iii) identification of the intermediate products, (iv) use of isotopes, (v) stereochemistry, (vi) kinetic analysis.

By far the most important tool to know the mechanism is the kinetics study and chemists have heavily relied on the results of such studies in absence of other evidences for the mechanism. Although the stoichiometry and identification of products are no less important, they indicate only the extent of reaction and the question, 'How are they formed?' remains unanswered. Kinetics can provide precise answers to the questions, 'What is the step of reaction which governs the speed of the overall reaction? In other words, what are the reactants in the rate-determining step? What is the nature of species? Whether they are ionic or neutral? If ionic, what is the nature and amount of charge?

The complete kinetics study involves the investigation of various factors as detailed below : (a) effect of concentration, leading to the determination of order with respect to the various reactants, (b) medium effect involving ionic strength and dielectric constant of the medium, leading to a possible prediction of the nature of species, (c) use of catalysts to know the intermediates, (d) use of isotopes to know the bonds being broken, (e) variation of pressure and temperature, leading to a possible prediction of the nature of species.

By far the most reliable factor for a kinetics study is the effect of concentration. Variation of concentration of a

reactant with fixed concentrations of other reactants, leads to the determination of order with respect to that reactant. In other words, such a study provides information as to what function the rate is of the concentration of that reactant. The determination of functional dependences of the concentration of the various reactants on the rate, leads to the rate expression.

It would be useful to discuss the effect of concentration on the rate in a systematic way either under the heading 'classified mechanisms' or according to various ways of interpreting the rate data. It is more logical to explain the rate data on the basis of postulated mechanisms rather than first giving the mechanisms and then predicting the experimental results. A number of exhaustive articles¹⁻³ have appeared on 'classified mechanisms', but there seem to be a few incomplete reports on the alternative classification. The reviews by Halpern³, Edwards *et al.*⁴ seem to be a combination of the two categories. The books by Espenson⁵, and Schmid and Sapunov⁶ appear to give alternative classification. The present article is perhaps the first exhaustive attempt to describe the interpretation of rate data, but this also by no means can be considered complete.

The various ways in which the rate data can be interpreted are as follows. One can add several other possibilities depending on the nature of the reaction and condition of experiment.

2. Various categories of reactions and mechanism

2.1. The rate is independent of the concentration of a reactant :

This is a commonly met situation and in such cases the rate-determining step does not involve the reactant and which participates only in the fast step. In the oxidation⁷ of Mn^{II} by peroxydisulfate catalyzed by Ag^I, the rate is independent of Mn^{II} and this occurs as follows :

In certain cases, the rate is independent of the concentration of a reactant only for its large concentrations and a plot of rate vs [reactant] yields a curve tending to a limiting value of rate. This can be explained either by a complex or adduct

formation between the two reactants, or by a mechanism in which the rate-determining step is preceded by an equilibrium step with the formation of a reactive intermediate. The two cases have been discussed at the appropriate places under the heading 'Order with respect to a reactant varies'. Incidentally, the above example also highlights the cases of all catalyzed reactions where the catalyst is a participant in the mechanism and appears in the rate law but has no role in stoichiometry.

2.2. *Order with respect to a reactant is less than the number of moles involved in the stoichiometric equation :*

This too is a common situation and the rate-determining step involves the number of moles of reactant equivalent to its order and the remaining number of moles of the reactant in the subsequent fast steps. In the oxidation⁸ of H₂O₂ by Ce⁴⁺ in acid sulfate solutions, Ce⁴⁺ is such reactant,

There is no direct evidence for the fast step and there could be other fast steps too. The above is a gross fast step on the basis of the stoichiometry of the reaction and the order with respect to Ce⁴⁺ being one.

2.3. *Order with respect to a reactant is more than the number of moles of the reactant in the stoichiometric equation :*

This is not a common situation. In such a case, the rate-determining step involves the number of moles of reactant equivalent to its order but subsequently one or more moles of the reactant are obtained back in fast steps. In the oxidation⁹ of H₂O₂ by Tl³⁺ in acid solutions, the order with respect to H₂O₂ is two, but the stoichiometry shows that only one mole of H₂O₂ reacts with one of Tl³⁺,

The rate-determining step involves a species, the concen-

tration of which is governed by the preceding rapid equilibrium step. It is said that perhaps a dimer of H₂O₂ (involving another rapid equilibrium step with small formation constant) is involved. The point to be noted is that the complex involving one mole of Tl³⁺ and two moles of H₂O₂ undergoes reaction releasing one mole of H₂O₂ unreacted and the overall stoichiometry is given by eqn. (9). A reaction¹⁰ between HgCl₂ and K₂C₂O₄ is a combination of both the situations discussed above. The order in HgCl₂ is one and that in K₂C₂O₄ is two, though the stoichiometry is given as eqn. (13),

If steps (15) to (17) are added, one would obtain equation (13).

2.4. *Inverse order with respect to a product :*

If one of the products inhibits the reaction the golden rule for the mechanism is that the rate-controlling step is preceded by a rapid equilibrium step in which that product is formed. The oxidation¹¹ of Cr³⁺ by Ce⁴⁺ in acid solutions occurs by such a mechanism in which the product, Ce³⁺ inhibits the reaction,

Ce³⁺ is the product which inhibits the reaction and it is formed in a rapid equilibrium preceding the rate-controlling step. There is an additional fast step in which the third mole of Ce⁴⁺ should be used up according to the stoichiometric eqn. (18). Also Cr⁵⁺ formed in step (21) is highly reactive and it must be further oxidized to Cr⁶⁺. Incidentally, this example is a combination of inhibition by a product and situation 2.2. It is obvious that in all such cases reactive

intermediates are formed; HO₂ in situation 2.2. and Cr⁴⁺ and Cr⁵⁺ in the present case.

2.5. *Inverse order with respect to a species which does not appear in the stoichiometric equation, but appears in the rate law :*

The reaction¹² of OCl⁻ with iodide is inhibited by hydroxyl ions. The details are given below :

For such a situation the same rule is followed as given in the previous category with the additional fact that the product formed in the rapid equilibrium step is subsequently used up in the fast step so that it does not appear in the stoichiometric equation.

2.6. *Order with respect to a reactant varies or is fractional with the variation in its concentration :*

This is a complicated but significant situation of concentration-rate dependence from the viewpoint of mechanism and can be interpreted in one of the following ways.

2.6.1. *Chain mechanism :* It may be a chain reaction, provided it has also other characteristics of a chain mechanism. The well known reaction¹³ between hydrogen and bromine is a chain mechanism and has a rate law which shows fractional order with respect to bromine and it varies with its concentration. The following are the details :

$$\text{where, } k = 2k_2(k_1/k_5)^{1/2} \text{ and } k' = k_4/k_3$$

It is obvious from the rate law that in the initial stages of the reaction, when [HBr] would be too small, the order in Br₂ would be half. In the presence of large concentration of HBr, the order in Br₂ would be 3/2.

2.6.2. *Reaction may occur by more than one path and the orders with respect to a reactant are different in different paths :* The reaction¹⁴ of H₂P₂O₈²⁻ and I⁻ occurs by three paths. The order in iodide and hydrogen ion varies between zero and one :

The first term of the rate law is independent of [H⁺] and the third term is independent of [I⁻]. Peroxodiphosphate can exist in several forms depending on the pH of the system. In the pH range employed in the investigation, H₂P₂O₈²⁻ is the predominant species. It can directly react with iodide (rate constant, k₁). It can be protonated and H₃P₂O₈⁻ formed may react with iodide (k₂). H₃P₂O₈⁻ can also undergo hydrolysis at the comparable rate (k₃) forming peroxomonophosphate, H₂PO₅⁻ which reacts with iodide in a fast step. It is not difficult to recognise these steps and can be known by making suitable plots.

Another example which is more complicated, is the reaction¹⁵ between nitrite and sulfite ions in a pH range where NO₂⁻ and HSO₃⁻ are the predominant species. The reaction is followed by estimating nitrite colorimetrically. The orders in sulfite and hydrogen ion vary between zero and two. Hydroxylamine disulfonate is the product. Following are the details for the reaction :

$$\text{Rate law : } -d[\text{NO}_2^-]/dt = k_1 K_1 [\text{H}^+]^2 [\text{NO}_2^-] + k_2 K_1 [\text{H}^+] [\text{NO}_2^-] [\text{HSO}_3^-] + k_3 K_2 [\text{NO}_2^-] [\text{HSO}_3^-]^2 \quad (44)$$

One can notice from the rate law that all the three terms have different HSO_3^- dependence. A plot of rate versus $[\text{HSO}_3^-]$ at constant concentrations of other reactants would be a curve making an intercept on the rate-axis. A plot of $(\text{rate}/[\text{NO}_2^-] - \text{Intercept})/[\text{HSO}_3^-]$ vs $[\text{HSO}_3^-]$ would be linear with non-zero intercept from which $k_2 K_1$ and $k_3 K_2$ can be calculated.

2.6.3. A reactant may be present in two or more forms and one or more of such species may be reactive : Ce^{4+} in acid sulfate solutions exists^{16,17} in the form of a number of complexes as shown below (K values at 25°) :

If the concentrations of Ce^{4+} and HSO_4^- are comparable and one attempts to determine the order with respect to Ce^{4+} , it would increase or decrease depending on the reactivity of the different complexes. In most cases a plot of rate vs $[\text{Ce}^{4+}]$ at fixed $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ would give a profile, the position of maximum depending on the reactivity and the formation constants of different complexes. If large excess of $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ is present, there is no difficulty in the determination of order since the total Ce^{4+} would be present as ultimate complex

and its concentration would be equal to $[\text{Ce}^{4+}]$.

A better example¹⁸ is provided by the system of Tl^{3+} in the presence of chloride ions, where Tl^{3+} is present as chloro complexes (all K values at 25°) :

Large concentration of chloride ions cannot be employed in a reaction since these ions are either greatly accelerating or greatly inhibiting the rate. In case of catalysis, the reactivity of the complexes is in the order, $\text{TlCl}_4^- > \text{TlCl}_3 > \text{TlCl}_2^+ > \text{TlCl}^{2+}$, and in case of inhibition, the reactivity is reversed. Since the concentration of Tl^{3+} and Cl^- are comparable in a system, any variation of Tl^{3+} at fixed $[\text{Cl}^-]$ for the determination of order would lead to a curve as the above $[\text{Ce}^{4+}]$ profile. However, in this case too if $[\text{Cl}^-]$ is about $10[\text{Tl}^{3+}]$ or more, the order in Tl^{3+} can be determined. If the successive formation constants of such a system are large, as in the present case K_1 and K_2 and to some extent K_3 are, there is simple way to determine¹⁹ the order in respect of the metal ion without resorting to large concentrations of the ligand. In the reaction of Tl^{3+} with H_3PO_2 in the presence of chloride ions, if the concentrations of Tl^{3+} and Cl^- are varied in such a way that the ratio $[\text{Cl}^-]/[\text{Tl}^{3+}]$ is constant (either 1, 2 or 3), the rate increases in proportion to Tl^{3+}

Fig. 1. A plot showing the course of a single kinetics experiment for the $\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}-\text{H}_3\text{PO}_2$ reaction with $[\text{Tl}^{3+}]_{\text{T}} = 6.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Cl}^-]_{\text{T}} = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 1.01 \text{ M}$, $[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_2] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$.

indicating first order in Tl^{3+} . The role of chloride ions with respect to the formation of different reactive species is shown in a single experiment²⁰ (Fig. 1). As the reaction proceeds, the concentration of Tl^{3+} decreases and consequently the ratio ($[Cl^-]/[Tl^{3+}]$) increases. The decrease in the concentration of Tl^{3+} is compensated by the formation of more reactive chloro-complexes and the rate is almost constant until the ratio becomes greater than two. Now the decrease in $[Tl^{3+}]$ is more than compensated by the greater reactivity of $TlCl_3$ or $TlCl_4^-$. Normal disappearance of Tl^{3+} is observed only after when the ratio is four.

2.6.4. Rate-determining step is preceded by a slow equilibrium step : In the oxidation²¹ of iron(II) with Tl^{3+} in acid perchlorate solutions, the order in iron(II) varies from 1 to 2 with the decrease in $[Fe^{2+}]$, and the reaction is inhibited by Fe^{3+} . This is therefore a combination of two situations. Following are the details at fixed $[H^+]$:

The rate law shows that in the initial stages of the reaction when $[Fe^{3+}]$ is small; the first term in the denominator is negligible and hence the order in Fe^{2+} is one. If sufficient Fe^{3+} is added to the reaction mixture, $k_2 [Fe^{3+}]$ becomes much larger than $k_3 [Fe^{2+}]$ and hence the order in Fe^{2+} becomes two. The rate law therefore reduces to a form like (19) and hence inhibition by a product is a special case in this situation. The form of the rate law under extreme conditions would depend on the relative values of $k_2 [Fe^{3+}]$ and $k_3 [Fe^{2+}]$. From the rate law (61), a plot of $(\text{rate}/[Fe^{2+}][Tl^{3+}])^{-1}$ vs $([Fe^{3+}]/[Fe^{2+}])$ would be linear with non-zero intercept equal to $1/k_1$ and slope equal to $k_2/k_3 k_1$. Thus in a system if $(\text{rate})^{-1}$ vs $[\text{product}]$ gives a straight-line with an intercept, a mechanism similar to (62) and (63) should be assigned to the reaction.

The reaction²² of hydroxylamine with Fe^{3+} in acid perchlorate solutions is similar in nature. The rate is inhibited by Fe^{2+} and the order in H^+ varies between 1 to 0 on increasing its concentration :

Some of the results of this reaction are interesting : (i) if $[Fe^{2+}] \gg [H^+]$, the rate is first order in $[H^+]$ and inverse first order in $[Fe^{2+}]$; (ii) if $[H^+] \gg [Fe^{2+}]$, the rate is independent of $[Fe^{2+}]$ and $[H^+]$; (iii) rate law (65) holds at 35°, but if the temperature is raised to 60° at fixed comparable concentrations of Fe^{2+} and H^+ , the rate behavior is similar to the case as in (i); (iv) if the temperature is lowered to 6° at fixed $[Fe^{2+}]$ and $[H^+]$, the rate behavior is similar to the case as in (ii). These observations lead to the conclusion that $k_2 \approx k_3$ at 35° and the temperature coefficient of k_2 is much larger than that of k_3 so that at 60°, $k_2 \gg k_3$, and at 6°, $k_2 \ll k_3$. In all cases where the rate is inhibited by one of the products, a reactive intermediate must be formed such as Tl^{2+} or NH_2OH^+ in the present examples and Cr^{4+} in the reaction of Ce^{4+} and Cr^{3+} .

If there is a situation such as given above, but one reactant is involved in the equilibrium step and the other reactant in the next step, it would lead to a kinetic behavior where the rate would be independent of the other reactant for its large concentrations. Oxidation of tris-phenanthroline²³ (or bipyridyl^{24,25} or terpyridyl²⁶) complex of iron(II) by peroxodiphosphate is independent of the oxidant for its large concentrations. For phenanthroline complex, following are the details :

For large concentrations of $P_2O_8^{4-}$, the dissociation of tris-complex into bis-complex is rate-controlling. The rate of dissociation without the oxidant is equal to the rate in presence of large $[P_2O_8^{4-}]$. Inhibition of the rate by phen is

additional evidence for this mechanism. Incidentally, all such cases highlight the necessity of investigating as wide range of concentration of a reactant as possible in order to have a complete picture of the mechanism.

Another reaction worth mentioning in this connection is the oxidation of hypophosphorous acid by CuCl_2 ²⁷, AgNO_3 ²⁸, iodine²⁹ and HgCl_2 ³⁰ which becomes independent of the oxidant concentration for its large concentrations. The rate law and the mechanism are the following :

$$\text{Rate law : } -d[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_2]/dt = k_3 k_1 [\text{H}_3\text{PO}_2] / [\text{H}^+][\text{Ox}]/(k_2[\text{H}^+] + k_3[\text{Ox}]) \quad (71)$$

$$-d[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_2]/dt = k_1[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_2][\text{H}^+] \quad (74)$$

Rate law (74) has been independently established³¹ by the exchange of radioactive hydrogen between H_3PO_2 and H_2O .

2.6.5. Complex formation : In a large number of cases where a metal ion reacts with a substrate or acts as a catalyst for two other reactants, the substrate acts both as a ligand and a reactant. In such a situation the order in substrate varies on account of complex formation. Hypophosphorous acid³² is oxidized by Tl^{3+} in acid perchlorate solutions through complex formation with the following details :

$$\text{Rate law : } -d[\text{Tl}^{3+}]/dt = kK[\text{Tl}^{3+}][\text{H}_3\text{PO}_2]/(1 + K[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_2]) \quad (76)$$

It is obvious from the rate law (76) that a plot of rate vs $[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_2]$ would yield a curve tending to a limiting value of rate at large concentrations of H_3PO_2 . A plot of $(\text{rate})^{-1}$ vs $[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_2]^{-1}$ would be linear with non-zero intercept from which k and K can be calculated. Thus if a plot of $(\text{rate})^{-1}$ vs $[\text{reactant}]^{-1}$ yields a straight-line with an intercept, the reaction should occur through intermediate complex formation with a mechanism shown above. Incidentally, this also is a case where the rate becomes independent of the

large concentrations of one of the reactants.

2.7. Rate decreases with the increase of concentration of a reactant :

There are situations when the rate of a reaction decreases with the increase in the concentration of a reactant but such a sweeping statement is misleading without specifying the conditions under which this happens. This would happen in a reaction of a metal ion with a ligand substrate where two or more complexes are formed and the complexes with larger content of ligand-substrate are less reactive or not reactive. The system³³ of Tl^{3+} and HNO_2 has three complexes, TlNO_2^{2+} , $\text{Tl}(\text{NO}_2)_2^+$ and $\text{Tl}(\text{NO}_2)_3$. The first and the third complexes are considered to be unreactive, and the second complex is considered to be reactive :

$$\text{Rate law : } -d[\text{Tl}^{3+}]/dt = kK_2[\text{Tl}^{3+}][\text{HNO}_2][\text{H}^+]/([\text{H}^+] + K_2[\text{HNO}_2][\text{H}^+] + K_2K_3[\text{HNO}_2]^2) \quad (80)$$

If one makes a plot of rate vs $[\text{HNO}_2]$, one would obtain a curve with a maximum in the rate. There is obviously a decrease in rate beyond a certain concentration of HNO_2 . From rate law (80), it is obvious that for large $[\text{HNO}_2]$, one can neglect the first two terms of the denominator and the rate law would reduce to (85) showing inverse dependence on HNO_2 :

$$-d[\text{Tl}^{3+}]/dt = k[\text{Tl}^{3+}][\text{H}^+]/k_3[\text{HNO}_2] \quad (85)$$

Beyond a certain concentration of HNO_2 , the concentration of reactive complex, $\text{Tl}(\text{NO}_2)_2^+$ decreases and that of unreactive complex $\text{Tl}(\text{NO}_2)_3$ increases and hence the rate decreases.

2.8. Various situations of complex formation and relative reactivities of the complexes :

In a system of metal ion and a ligand-reactant, one or more of intermediate complexes may be formed, and one or more of them may be reactive. In such a system, a plot of rate vs [ligand-reactant] would yield a curve corresponding

to one of the situations shown in Fig. 2. The exact number of complexes may not be known from the kinetic data, but these do provide some useful qualitative information as detailed below.

(i) The minimum number of complexes indicated by different figures is as follows : (a) – one, (b) – two, (c) –

mandelic acid, 2-isohydroxybutyric acid and lactic acid were found to be 5.8×10^{13} , 4.0×10^{12} , 2.3×10^9 , 2.2×10^6 and $4.4 \times 10^3 M^{-1}$, respectively, at 25° . In case of benzilic acid, only one complex was indicated kinetically, but potentiometric analysis indicates three complexes which probably have similar reactivities.

Fig. 2. Different situations of complex formation.

two, (d) – three, (e) – two, (f) – three, (g) – three, (h) – four.

(ii) From the concentration of the ligand corresponding to the maximum and limiting rates, one can have rough idea about the relative formation constants of the complexes in different cases. In case of limiting rates, it is possible to calculate kinetically the formation constant of a particular complex.

(iii) All these curves which are convex to the rate-axis in the initial stages (a, b, c and d), indicate that the first complex (most probably 1 : 1) is reactive. Curves which are concave to the rate-axis (e, f, g and h) indicate that the first complex is not reactive. Examples for each category has been mentioned in the figure itself. Since the oxidations of substituted glycolic acids with Ti^{3+} are slow at room temperature, the formation constants of the complexes can be determined potentiometrically and spectrophotometrically. In most cases, three complexes have been indicated potentiometrically. The gross formation constants³⁶ (β_n) for benzilic acid, phenyllactic acid,

2.9. Rate is dependent on the concentration of trace metal-ion impurities or is independent of the concentrations of both the main reactants :

Very often the inorganic redox reactions are monitored by the trace metal-ion impurities present in the reagents and distilled water. Some of the more common such metal-ions are Fe^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Os^{8+} . The role of these ions is to first react with one of the reactants and then get back to their original form by reacting with the other reactant. Oxidation⁴⁰ of ascorbic acid with peroxodiphosphate ($H_2P_2O_8^{2-}$) in acid solutions is one such example where Cu^{2+} present in traces slowly oxidises ascorbic acid and Cu^+ is formed. The latter is oxidized by peroxodiphosphate in a fast step since the rate is independent of $[H_2P_2O_8^{2-}]$. Although the reaction of Cu^+ with $H_2P_2O_8^{2-}$ has not been reported so far, it is likely to be fast. The reaction⁴¹ of ascorbic acid with Cu^{2+} is well known. Following is the mechanism of the reaction in acid buffers :

The reaction is completely checked in the presence of edta, obviously because Cu^{2+} is complexed and free aquo- Cu^{2+} is not available for oxidation. In contrast with this, Cu^{II} -edta complex and not aquo- Cu^{II} , is a catalyst in the oxidation⁴² of hexacyanoferrate(II) with $\text{H}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$. The mechanism of the reaction is complicated, but at constant $[\text{H}^+]$, it can be simplified to the following :

and the rate law is

$$-\frac{d[\text{H}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]}{dt} = k_1 k_3 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}] [\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-(edta)}_6] / (k_2 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] + k_3 [\text{H}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]) \quad (91)$$

An interesting example of catalysis by trace metal-ion impurity, is the oxidation⁴³ of pyridine with hexacyanoferrate(III) in alkaline solutions. The rate is independent of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$. The rate increases and becomes limiting with the increase of [pyridine]. Thus for large [pyridine] ($>0.1 M$), the rate is independent of both the main reactants. Such a situation is impossible unless there is something else in the system to monitor the reaction. The trace impurity responsible for catalysis was found to be Os^{VIII} . Following is the probable mechanism :

Deliberate addition of traces of Os^{8+} significantly catalyses the reaction and the mechanism in the presence of added Os^{8+} is identical to the one described above. The rate is independent of large [pyridine] since it is the decomposition of the complex which is rate-controlling and the concen-

tration of the complex is independent for large [pyridine]. However, the results were inconclusive since it could not be ascertained whether Os^{8+} impurity was present in the hydroxide solutions. The hydroxide and Os^{8+} dependences of the rate were quite complicated. Fe^{3+} and Cu^{2+} had no effect on the rate.

These are some of the more common situations of the effect of concentration on the rate which one comes across during a kinetics study. Other less common situations are, formation of binuclear complexes⁴⁴, formation of dimer⁴⁵, acceleration⁴⁶ by one of the products etc. and the kinetic treatment is complicated. However, a careful and judicious planning of the kinetics work more often solves the problem of mechanism, howsoever complicated it may be. Although major role in this is played by the effect of concentration on the rate, it is advisable and desirable to have additional independent evidences for the mechanism. It would be worthwhile to describe here the results of one reaction in detail leading to its mechanism.

3. A typical complicated reaction

Oxidation of thiocyanate^{47,48} ion with thallium(III) in acid perchlorate solutions is quite complicated. The kinetics were followed by estimating Tl^{3+} iodometrically. Following is the stoichiometry :

Some of the significant results are :

- A plot of rate vs $[\text{SCN}^-]$ at fixed $[\text{Tl}^{3+}]$ has a peak value.
- The order in Tl^{3+} when $[\text{SCN}^-] \gg [\text{Tl}^{3+}]$, is two.
- The order in SCN^- when $[\text{Tl}^{3+}] \gg [\text{SCN}^-]$, is two.
- The total order when $[\text{Tl}^{3+}] = [\text{SCN}^-]$, is two and not four, since if the concentrations of the reactants are doubled, the rate increases four-fold.
- The reaction is fast for equal concentrations of the reactants and becomes slow by increasing or decreasing the concentration of any reactant at the fixed concentration of the other reactant.

(f) If the ratio of initial concentrations, $([\text{Tl}^{3+}]/[\text{SCN}^-])$ is less than three but more than 1, a plot of concentration of any reactant vs time is not regular. The reaction becomes fast when $[\text{Tl}^{3+}] = [\text{SCN}^-]$. One typical run is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Plots of the concentrations of Ti^{III} (initially 4.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³); (O) and SCN⁻ (initially 2.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³) vs time at [HClO₄] = 2.0 mol dm⁻³ and 20°.

Some important conclusions :

(i) Three complexes seem to be formed. Ti(SCN)₂²⁺ (1 : 1 complex) has high formation constant and is the only reactive complex. The other two complexes perhaps of the composition Ti(SCN)₂⁺ (1 : 2) and Ti₂(SCN)₅⁵⁺ (2 : 1) are not reactive.

(ii) The order in reactive complex is two. Thus two moles of this complex are involved in the rate-determining step, perhaps in the form of a dimer such as

Following mechanism may be suggested on the basis of the above information :

At constant [H⁺] and under the condition, [SCN⁻] >> [Ti³⁺], rate law (101) is obtained,

$$-d[\text{Ti}^{3+}]/dt = 3 kK_4 [\text{Ti}^{3+}]^2 / (1 + k_2 [\text{SCN}^-])^2 \quad (101)$$

Rate law was verified from a plot of $([\text{Ti}^{3+}]/(\text{rate})^{1/2})^{-1}$ vs [SCN⁻] which was linear with non-zero intercept. From this kK_4 and K_2 were found to be $2.2 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and 24 M^{-1} , respectively, at 20° and $I = 2.2 \text{ M}$. The rate law when $[\text{Ti}^{3+}] \gg [\text{SCN}^-]$, is as follows :

$$-d[\text{Ti}^{3+}]/dt = 3 kK_4 [\text{SCN}^-]^2 / (1 + K_3 [\text{Ti}^{3+}])^2 \quad (102)$$

In support of this, a plot of $([\text{SCN}^-]/(\text{rate})^{1/2})^{-1}$ vs Ti^{3+} was linear with non-zero intercept yielding the values of kK_4 and K_3 equal to $2.1 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and 90 M^{-1} , respectively, at the same temperature and ionic strength. Similar values of kK_4 under two extreme conditions show the validity of the mechanism.

Having emphasized the importance of role of concentration in kinetics and having given a rosy picture about the determination of mechanism, one should not forget that a mechanism is a mental model devised to explain the observed facts and this we do so on the basis of current theories and principles. If these undergo a change, the mechanism also has to be suitably modified. Similarly, if in future an observation is made which can not be explained on the basis of the current mechanism, then also the mechanism has to be given up or suitably modified. There is no last word to mechanism of a reaction. All that can be said about a particular mechanism, is that it is the most probable one which can explain most of the observed facts.

4. Reaction scheme and mechanism

The two terms 'reaction scheme' and 'mechanism' are in general synonymously used, one for the other without any distinction. However, there is a subtle difference between the two.

A reaction scheme is a bunch of several steps occurring simultaneously and/or consecutively. The mechanism may be defined as detailed and pictorial representation of the reaction scheme itself.

Gross reactants and intermediates form part of the reaction scheme, but the exact nature of these species form part of the mechanism. The information about the reaction scheme is provided by the kinetics, but the mechanism is known from the spectroscopic and other physical methods in addition to kinetic analysis. A reaction scheme is almost firmly established. At best it can be enlarged to accommodate additional facts and evidences. A mechanism on the other hand, which is based on the current theories about structure and bonding, may be altogether disproven. In terms of

reaction scheme the achievements of kinetics can be clearly recognised. In terms of mechanism, it is the limitations of kinetics rather than its merits, which are highlighted. Nyholm⁴⁹ has very rightly said, "Kinetics to mechanism equals facts to fiction!"

5. Transition state – a reality now

In the beginning of this article, it was mentioned that it is not possible to see the course of a chemical reaction and that transition state is a hypothetical entity, different than real intermediate, but a discovery⁵⁰ has proved that the transition state is as good as any intermediate though shortlived. It has been possible to obtain the structure of the transition state with the help of short burst of lasers in the case of the reaction between CO₂ and H to produce CO and OH. This is a major breakthrough in the field of reaction mechanism. This opens up a possibility of obtaining a picture of series of events occurring in a millionth of a billionth of a second, and the picture can be seen later like an ordinary film. This is a landmark in kinetics and modern chemistry.

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